

Study on the development of neutrosophic triplet ring and neutrosophic triplet field

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Definition 1. Let $(NTR, *, \#)$ be a set together with two binary operations $*$ and $\#$. Then NTR is called a neutrosophic triplet ring if the following conditions are holds.

- 1) $(NTR, *)$ is a commutative neutrosophic triplet group with respect to $*$.
- 2) $(NTR, \#)$ is a semineutrosophic triplet monoid with respect to $\#$.
- 3) $a\#(b*c) = (a\#b)*(a\#c)$ and $(b*c)\#a = (b\#a)*(c\#a)$ for all $a, b, c \in NTR$.

Example 1. Consider Z_{10} . Let $NTR = \{0, 2, 4, 6, 8\} \subseteq Z_{10}$. Define two operations $*$ and $\#$ on NTR by the following way respectively:

1. $a*b = a \times b \pmod{10}$ for all $a, b \in NTR$.
2. $a\#b = \max(a, b)$ for all $a, b \in NTR$.

Then clearly $(NTR, *)$ is a commutative neutrosophic triplet group with respect to multiplication modulo 10, as NTR is well defined and associative. Also $(0, 0, 0), (2, 6, 8), (4, 6, 4), (6, 6, 6)$ and $(8, 6, 2)$ are neutrosophic triplets in NTR with respect to multiplication modulo 10. Clearly $a*b = b*a$ for all $a, b \in NTR$.

Now $(R, \#)$ is a semineutrosophic triplet monoid with respect to $\#$. Since $\max(0, 0) = 0, \max(0, 2) = 2, \max(2, 4) = 4, \max(4, 6) = 6$ and $\max(6, 8) = 8$, that is for every $a \in NTR$, there exist at least one $neut(a)$ in NTR .

Finally $\#$ is distributive over $*$. For instance

$$2\#(4*6) = (2\#4)*(2\#6)$$

$$2\#(4 \times 6) = (2\#4) \times (2\#6)$$

$$2\#4 = \max(2, 4) \times \max(2, 6)$$

$$\max(2, 4) = 4 \times 6$$

$$4 = 4, \text{ and so on.}$$

Thus for all $a, b, c \in NTR$, $\#$ is distributive over $*$. Therefore $(NTR, *, \#)$ is a neutrosophic triplet ring.

Definition. Let $(NTR, *, \#)$ be a neutrosophic triplet ring and let $0 \neq a \in NTR$. If there exist a non-zero neutrosophic triplet $b \in NTR$ such that $b\#a = 0$. Then b is called left neutrosophic triplet zero divisors of a . Similarly a neutrosophic triplet $b \in NTR$ is called a right neutrosophic triplet zero divisor if $a\#b = 0$.

A neutrosophic triplet zero divisor is one which is left neutrosophic triplet zero divisor as well as right neutrosophic triplet zero divisor.

Theorem. Let NTR be a neutrosophic triplet ring and $a, b \in NTR$. If $b\#a = a\#b = 0$, then

1. $neut(a)\#neut(b) = neut(b)\#neut(a) = 0$ and
2. $anti(a)\#anti(b) = anti(b)\#anti(a) = 0$.

Proof 1. Let NTR be a neutrosophic triplet ring and $a, b \in NTR$ such that b is a neutrosophic triplet zero divisor of a . Then $a\#b = b\#a = 0$. Now consider

$$neut(a)\#neut(b) = neut(a\#b)$$

Or

$$= neut(0), \text{ since } a\#b = 0.$$

Or

$$= 0, \text{ as } neut(0) = 0.$$

Also

$$neut(b)\#neut(a) = neut(b\#a)$$

$$= neut(0), \text{ as } b\#a = 0$$

$$neut(0) = 0.$$

Hence $neut(a)\#neut(b) = neut(b)\#neut(a) = 0$.

2. The proof is similar to 1.

Definition. Let $(NTR, *, \#)$ be a neutrosophic triplet ring and let S be a subset of NTR . Then S is called a neutrosophic triplet subring of NTR if $(S, *, \#)$ is a neutrosophic triplet ring.

Definition. Let $(NTR, *, \#)$ be a neutrosophic triplet ring and I is a subset of NTR . Then I is called a neutrosophic triplet ideal of NTR if the following conditions are satisfied.

1. $(I, *)$ is a neutrosophic triplet subgroup of $(NTR, \#)$, and
2. For all $x \in I$ and $r \in NTR$, $x \# r \in I$ and $r \# x \in I$.

Theorem. Every neutrosophic triplet ideal is trivially a neutrosophic triplet subring but the converse is not true in general.

Remark. Let $(NTR, *, \#)$ is a neutrosophic triplet ring and let $a \in NTR$. Then the following are true.

1. $neut(a)$ and $anti(a)$ is not unique in NTR with respect to $*$.
2. $neut(a)$ and $anti(a)$ is not unique in NTR with respect to $\#$.

Theorem. Let $(NTR, *, \#)$ is a neutrosophic triplet ring. Then for any element a in a neutrosophic triplet ring NTR , one has $0 \# a = a \# 0 = 0$.

Definition. Let NTR is a neutrosophic triplet ring and let $a \in NTR$. Then a is called nilpotent neutrosophic triplet if $a^n = 0$, for some positive integer $n > 1$.

Theorem. Let NTR is a neutrosophic triplet ring and let $a \in NTR$. If a is a nilpotent neutrosophic triplet. Then the following are true.

1. $(neut(a))^n = 0$ and
2. $(anti(a))^n = 0$.

Proof: 1:

Suppose that a is a nilpotent neutrosophic triplet in a neutrosophic triplet ring NTR . Then by definition $a^n = 0$ for some positive integer $n > 1$. Now we consider Left hand side of 1:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Since} \quad (neut(a))^n &= (neut(a)) \# (neut(a))^{n-1} \\
 &= neut(a \# a^{n-1}) \\
 &= neut(a^n) \\
 &= neut(0), \text{ by definition.} \\
 &= 0.
 \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof.

2: The proof of 2 is similar to 1.

Integral Neutrosophic triplet domain

Definition: Let $(NTR, *, \#)$ be a neutrosophic triplet ring. Then NTR is called a commutative neutrosophic triplet ring if $a\#b = b\#a$ for all $a, b \in NTR$.

Definition: A commutative neutrosophic triplet ring NTR is called integral neutrosophic triplet domain if for all $a, b \in NTR$, $a\#b = 0$ implies $a = 0$ or $b = 0$.

Theorem: Let NTR be an integral neutrosophic triplet domain. Then the following are true.

1. $neut(a)\#neut(b) = 0$ implies $neut(a) = 0$ or $neut(b) = 0$ and
2. $anti(a)\#anti(b) = 0$ implies $anti(a) = 0$ or $anti(b) = 0$ for all $a, b \in NTR$.

Proof: 1.

Suppose that NTR is an integral neutrosophic triplet domain. Then for all $a, b \in NTR$, $a\#b = 0$ implies $a = 0$ or $b = 0$. Consider $neut(a)\#neut(b)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} neut(a)\#neut(b) &= neut(a\#b) \\ &= neut(a\#b) \\ &= neut(0), \text{ as } a\#b = 0. \\ neut(a)\#neut(b) &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Which implies that either $neut(a) = 0$ or $neut(b) = 0$.

2: The proof is similar to 1.

Proposition: A commutative neutrosophic triplet ring NTR is an integral neutrosophic triplet domain if and only if whenever $a, b, c \in NTR$ such that $a\#b = a\#c$ and $a \neq 0$, then $b = c$.

Proof: Suppose that NTR is an integral neutrosophic triplet domain and let $a, b, c \in NTR$. Since $a \neq 0$ and $a \in NTR$, a is not zero divisor then a is cancellable i.e.,

$$a\#b = a\#c \Rightarrow a\#b - a\#c = 0 \Rightarrow a\#(b - c) = 0$$

Since $a \neq 0, b - c = 0 \Rightarrow b = c$.

\Leftarrow Let $a \in NTR$, such that $a \neq 0$, then by hypothesis a is cancellable. a is not a zero divisor. NTR is an integral neutrosophic triplet domain.

Neutrosophic Triplet Ring Homomorphism.

Definition: Let $(NTR_1, *, \#)$ and (NTR_2, \oplus, \otimes) be two neutrosophic triplet rings. Let $f : NTR_1 \rightarrow NTR_2$ be a mapping. Then f is called neutrosophic triplet ring homomorphism if the following conditions are true.

1. $f(a * b) = f(a) \oplus f(b)$.
2. $f(a \# b) = f(a) \otimes f(b)$, for all $a, b \in NTR_1$.
3. $f(\text{neut}(a)) = \text{neut}(f(a))$.
4. $f(\text{anti}(a)) = \text{anti}(f(a))$.

Neutrosophic Triplet Field

Definition. Let $(NTR, *, \#)$ be a neutrosophic triplet set together with two binary operations $*$ and $\#$. Then $(NTR, *, \#)$ is called neutrosophic triplet field if the following conditions are holds.

1. $(NTR, *)$ is a commutative neutrosophic triplet group with respect to $*$.
2. $(NTR, \#)$ is a neutrosophic triplet group with respect to $\#$.
3. $a \# (b * c) = (a \# b) * (a \# c)$ and $(b * c) \# a = (b \# a) * (c \# a)$ for all $a, b, c \in NTF$.

Example. Let X be a set and $P(X)$ be the power set of X . Then $(P(X), \cup, \cap)$ is a neutrosophic triplet field if $\text{neut}(A) = A$ and $\text{anti}(A) = A$ for all $A \in P(X)$.

Proposition. A neutrosophic triplet field NTF has no neutrosophic triplet zero divisors.

Proof. Suppose that a neutrosophic triplet field NTF has neutrosophic triplet zero divisor say $0 \neq a, b$. Then by definition of neutrosophic triplet zero divisor, $a \# b = 0$. This implies either $a = 0$ or $b = 0$ which clearly contradicts our supposition. Hence this shows that a neutrosophic triplet field NTF has no zero divisors.

Proposition. A neutrosophic triplet field NTF has always $\text{anti}(a)$'s for all $a \in NTF$.

Proof. The proof is straightforward.

Theorem. If NTF is a field and $a \in NTF$. Then $a \# 0 = 0$.

Proof. Since $(a \# 0) * (a \# 0) = a \# (0 * 0)$, by commutative law.

Also $0 * 0 = 0$. Thus $(a \# 0) * (a \# 0) = a \# 0$ which implies $a \# 0 = 0$.

Theorem. Every finite integral neutrosophic triplet domain NTD is a neutrosophic triplet field NTF .

Proof. Let NTD be a finite integral neutrosophic triplet domain. NTD is commutative ring with unity. To show that D is a neutrosophic triplet field NTF , it is enough to show that every non-zero element of NTD is a unit. Let the elements of NTD be labelled as

$$r_0 (= 0_{NTD}) \text{ and } r_1 (= 1_{NTD}), r_2, \dots, r_n.$$

Let $r_i \in NTD$ such that $r_i \neq 0_{NTD} = r_0$. Thus consider the elements

$$r_i \# r_0, r_i \# r_1, \dots, r_i \# r_n \in NTD \text{ and are distinct } (\because \text{if } r_i \# r_s = r_i \# r_k \Rightarrow r_s = r_k).$$

Now since $1_{NTD} \in NTD$, therefore there must be some j such that $r_i \# r_j = r_j \# r_i \Rightarrow r_j$ is inverse of r_i i.e. r_i is invertible or r_i is a unit. Thus NTD is a neutrosophic triplet field NTF .

Theorem. Every neutrosophic triplet field NTF is an integral neutrosophic triplet domain NTD .

Proof. Let NTF be a neutrosophic triplet field. Then NTF is a commutative neutrosophic triplet ring with unity. To show that NTF is an integral neutrosophic triplet domain NTD , it is enough to show that every non-zero element is not a zero-divisor.

Now suppose that $a, b \in NTF$ such that $a \neq 0$ and $a \# b = 0$. Consider $a \# b = 0$, since $a \neq 0 \in NTF$. $a \# b = a \# 0$ ($\because a \# 0 = 0$) $\Rightarrow a \# b - a \# 0 = 0 \Rightarrow a \# (b - 0) = 0 \Rightarrow a \neq 0, b - 0 = 0 \Rightarrow b = 0$. a is not a zero-divisor.

Theorem. If $f: NTR_1 \rightarrow NTR_2$ is a neutrosophic triplet ring homomorphism then

(1) If S is a neutrosophic triplet subring of NTR_1 , then $f(S)$ is a neutrosophic triplet subring of NTR_2 .

(2) If U is a neutrosophic triplet ring of NTR_2 , then $f^{-1}(U)$ is a neutrosophic triplet subring of NTR_1 .

(3) If I is a neutrosophic triplet ideal of NTR_2 , then $f^{-1}(I)$ is a neutrosophic triplet ideal of NTR_1 .

(4) If f is onto, then $f(I)$ is a neutrosophic triplet ideal of NTR_2 .
(I is neutrosophic triplet ideal of NTR_1).

Proof. Given that $f: NTR_1 \rightarrow NTR_2$ is a neutrosophic triplet ring homomorphism.

(1) If S is a neutrosophic triplet subring of NTR_1 , we need to show that $f(S)$ is a neutrosophic triplet subring of NTR_2 . To do this, $f(S) \neq \emptyset$, ($\because S$ is a neutrosophic triplet subring) and

$f(0_{NTR_1}) = 0_S$. Also let $a, b \in f(S) \Rightarrow \exists \acute{a}, \acute{b} \in S$ such that $f(\acute{a}) = a$ and $f(\acute{b}) = b$. Since S is neutrosophic triplet subring so for $\acute{a}, \acute{b} \in S \Rightarrow \acute{a} - \acute{b} \in S$ and $\acute{a} \# \acute{b} \in S$.

Consider $f(\acute{a} - \acute{b}) = f(\acute{a} * (-\acute{b})) = f(\acute{a}) \oplus f(-\acute{b}) = f(\acute{a}) - f(\acute{b}), (\because f(-\acute{b}) = -f(\acute{b}))$,

i.e., $f(\acute{a} - \acute{b}) = f(\acute{a}) - f(\acute{b}) = a - b \in f(S)$.

Also $f(\acute{a} \# \acute{b}) = f(\acute{a}) \otimes f(\acute{b}) = a \otimes b \in f(S)$.

$f(S)$ is a neutrosophic triplet subring of NTR_2 .

(2) If U is a neutrosophic triplet subring of NTR_2 , then $f^{-1}(U)$ is a neutrosophic triplet subring of NTR_1 , so $f^{-1}(U) = \{r \in U \mid r \in NTR_1 \text{ \& } f(r) \in U\}$. Clearly $f^{-1}(U) \neq \emptyset, \because U$ is a neutrosophic triplet subring. Let $a, b \in f^{-1}(U) \Rightarrow f(a), f(b) \in U$. Since U is a neutrosophic triplet subring of $NTR_2 \Rightarrow f(a) - f(b) \in U$ and $f(a) \# f(b) \in U$.

Now $f(a) - f(b) = f(a - b) \in U \Rightarrow a - b \in f^{-1}(U)$.

And $f(a) \# f(b) = f(a \otimes b) \in U \Rightarrow a \otimes b \in f^{-1}(U)$.

$f^{-1}(U)$ is a neutrosophic triplet subring of NTR_1 .

(3) If I is an ideal of NTR_2 , we need to show that $f^{-1}(I)$ is an ideal of NTR_1 . Since $f^{-1}(I) \neq \emptyset, \because I$ is an ideal of NTR_2 . Also let $a, b \in f^{-1}(I) \Rightarrow f(a), f(b) \in I$. Since I is an ideal of $NTR_2, f(a) - f(b) \in I$ and $f(a) \# f(b) \in I$.

Now consider,

$$f(a) - f(b) = f(a - b) \in I \Rightarrow a - b \in f^{-1}(I)$$

and

$$f(a) \# f(b) = f(a \otimes b) \in I \Rightarrow a \otimes b \in f^{-1}(I).$$

Let $f(r) \in NTR_2$ and $a \in f^{-1}(I) \Rightarrow f(a) \in I, f(r) \in NTR_2$ and since I is an ideal of NTR_2 ,

$$f(a) \# f(r) \in I \text{ and } f(r) \# f(a) \in I,$$

$$f(a \otimes r) \in I \text{ and } f(r \otimes a) \in I,$$

$$(a \otimes r) \in f^{-1}(I) \text{ and } (r \otimes a) \in f^{-1}(I).$$

Hence $f^{-1}(I)$ is an ideal of NTR_1 .

(4) If f is onto, then $f(I)$ is an ideal of NTR_2 , where I is an ideal of NTR_1 . Since $f(I) \neq \emptyset$. Let $a, b \in f(I) \Rightarrow \exists \acute{a}, \acute{b} \in I$ such that $f(\acute{a}) = a$ and $f(\acute{b}) = b$. Now since I is an ideal of NTR_1 , so for $\acute{a}, \acute{b} \in I \Rightarrow \acute{a} - \acute{b} \in I$. Consider,

$$a - b = f(\acute{a}) - f(\acute{b}) = f(\acute{a} - \acute{b}) \in f(I),$$

$$a - b \in f(I).$$

And let $a \in f(I)$ and let $t \in NTR_2 \Rightarrow \exists \acute{a} \in I$ such that $f(\acute{a}) = a$, also f is onto \Rightarrow for $t \in NTR_2 \exists r \in NTR_1$ such that $f(r) = t$.

Since I is an ideal of NTR_2 , so $\acute{a}\#r$ and $r\#\acute{a} \in I$. Now

$t\#a = f(r)\otimes f(\acute{a}) = f(r\otimes\acute{a}) \in f(I), t\#a \in f(I)$. Similarly $a\#t \in f(I)$. Hence $f(I)$ is an ideal of NTR_2 .